

CERVICAL RANGE OF MOTION, POSTURE, AND QUALITY OF LIFE IN INDIVIDUALS WITH HYPERTENSION: A CROSS-SECTIONAL OBSERVATIONAL STUDY

HİPERTANSİYONLU BİREYLERDE SERVİKAL HAREKET AÇIKLIĞI, POSTÜR VE YAŞAM KALİTESİ: KESİTSEL GÖZLEMSEL BİR ÇALIŞMA

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ABSTRACT

Objective: Hypertension is not only associated with cardiovascular morbidity and mortality; it is also a systemic condition that can affect musculoskeletal system functions and quality of life. The aim of this study was to evaluate cervical range of motion, postural alignment, and quality of life in individuals with hypertension.

Methods: This cross-sectional observational study included 27 individuals diagnosed with hypertension and 27 healthy controls (mean age=57.29 ± 8.72). Cervical range of motion was assessed using a CROM device; posture was evaluated with the New York Posture Analysis Scale; and quality of life was measured using the SF-36 questionnaire.

Results: Cervical flexion, extension, right/left lateral flexion, and right/left rotation angles were significantly lower in the hypertension group (p<0.05). The total score of the New York Posture Analysis Scale was also lower in the hypertension group (p<0.01). The mental health subscale of the SF-36 was significantly lower in individuals with hypertension (p<0.01). No significant differences were found between groups in other SF-36 subscales (p>0.05).

Conclusion: Hypertension is associated with reduced cervical mobility and impaired postural alignment, and particularly negatively affects the mental health dimension of quality of life. These findings highlight the clinical importance of incorporating musculoskeletal assessment and psychosocial monitoring into comprehensive hypertension management.

Keywords: Cervical Spine, Hypertension, Posture, Quality of Life, Range of Motion.

ÖZET

Amaç: Hipertansiyon yalnızca kardiyovasküler morbidite ve mortalite ile ilişkili değildir; aynı zamanda kas-iskelet sistemi fonksiyonlarını ve yaşam kalitesini etkileyebilen sistemik bir durumdur. Bu çalışmanın amacı, hipertansiyonlu bireylerde servikal eklem hareket açıklığını, postüral hizalanmayı ve yaşam kalitesini değerlendirmektir.

Yöntem: Bu kesitsel gözlemsel çalışmaya hipertansiyon tanısı almış 27 birey ve 27 sağlıklı kontrol dâhil edildi (ortalama yaş = 57,29 ± 8,72). Servikal eklem hareket açıklığı CROM cihazı kullanılarak değerlendirildi; postür New York Postür Analiz Skalası ile analiz edildi; yaşam kalitesi ise SF-36 anketi ile ölçüldü.

Bulgular: Servikal fleksiyon, ekstansiyon, sağ/sol lateral fleksiyon ve sağ/sol rotasyon açıları hipertansiyon grubunda anlamlı olarak daha düşüktü (p<0,05). New York Postür Analiz Skalası toplam puanı da hipertansiyon grubunda daha düşük bulundu (p<0,01). SF-36'nın mental sağlık alt ölçeği hipertansiyonlu bireylerde anlamlı düzeyde daha düşüktü (p<0,01). Diğer SF-36 alt ölçekleri açısından gruplar arasında anlamlı fark bulunmadı (p>0,05).

Sonuç: Hipertansiyon, azalmış servikal hareketliliğe ve bozulmuş postüral hizalanmaya eşlik etmekte ve yaşam kalitesinin özellikle mental sağlık boyutunu olumsuz yönde etkilemektedir. Bu bulgular, hipertansiyon yönetiminde kas-iskelet sistemi değerlendirmesinin ve psikososyal izlemin bütüncül yaklaşımla ele alınmasının klinik önemini vurgulamaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Eklem Hareket Açıklığı, Hipertansiyon, Postür, Servikal Omurga, Yaşam Kalitesi

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INTRODUCTION

Hypertension is recognized as one of the most significant public health problems today due to its rapidly increasing global prevalence and high mortality rates. Global epidemiological data indicate that hypertension is associated with serious health outcomes such as cardiovascular disease, stroke, and renal failure, and that its management is particularly challenging in developing countries (Addo et al., 2007; Mills et al., 2020). This condition imposes a substantial burden not only through its physiological effects but also on individuals' quality of life. Studies report that individuals with hypertension exhibit significantly lower quality of life across physical, emotional, and social domains, and that chronic disease awareness and stress mechanisms further reinforce this decline (Carvalho et al., 2013; Korhonen et al., 2011).

Hypertension is closely associated with the autonomic nervous system and psychological status. Increased sympathetic nervous system activity is a fundamental component of hypertension pathophysiology, and anxiety and depression are reported to be more prevalent in individuals with hypertension (Bajkó et al., 2012). This suggests that autonomic imbalance affects not only cardiovascular outcomes but also quality of life through behavioral and emotional changes.

In recent years, the relationship between hypertension and musculoskeletal system functions has been increasingly investigated. In particular, the role of cervical spine alignment in autonomic regulation has attracted attention. It has been reported that realignment of the atlas vertebra significantly reduces systolic and diastolic blood pressure, suggesting that the close relationship between cervical structures and the vascular and neurological systems may play a role in blood pressure regulation (Bakris et al., 2007). Forward head posture, by causing mechanical stress and proprioceptive dysfunction in cervical segments, may increase blood pressure, and higher peripheral arterial pressure has been demonstrated in individuals with postural abnormalities (Kadu et al., 2019). Interventions aimed at correcting posture have been reported to reduce systolic and diastolic blood pressure (Malik et al., 2023).

In addition, strong associations have been reported between a sedentary lifestyle, cervical region dysfunction, and hypertension. Prolonged sitting and low physical activity have been shown to increase neck disability and negatively affect blood pressure regulation (Pradnyadewi et al., 2024). These findings suggest that cervical function and postural control may have important effects not only on musculoskeletal health but also on the cardiovascular system.

Hypertension appears to be a multidimensional health condition that should be addressed not only through hemodynamic parameters but also in relation to posture, cervical functions, lifestyle behaviors, and quality of life. In this context, the aim of the present study is to examine cervical range of motion, postural alignment, and quality of life in individuals with hypertension.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design and Setting

This cross-sectional observational study was designed to investigate cervical range of motion, postural alignment, and quality of life in individuals with hypertension. The research was conducted between July 2025 and November 2025 at Zonguldak Bahçelievler Family Health Center. The study was carried out in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki, and informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to assessments. Ethics committee approval has been received from 21/05/2025 date and 2025-10/11 number of Zonguldak Bülent Ecevit University Non-Interventional Clinical Research Ethics Committee. The study was conducted in compliance with ethical guidelines and voluntary participation principles.

Participants

The study sample consisted of individuals aged 40–70 years who presented to the Zonguldak Bahçelievler Family Health Center. Participants were divided into two groups: 27 individuals diagnosed with hypertension constituted the hypertension group (HG), while 27 individuals without a history of hypertension formed the control group (CG).

Inclusion criteria were being between 40 and 70 years of age, willingness to voluntarily participate in the study, and having a medical diagnosis of hypertension for the HG, while absence of any history of hypertension was required for the CG. Individuals with a history of trauma or surgery affecting the cervical region, neurological disorders, vestibular dysfunctions, or medical conditions affecting the musculoskeletal system were excluded from the study.

Outcome Measures

All assessments were conducted in a single session on the same day by experienced physiotherapists, adhering to standardized protocols to enhance measurement reliability. Tests were performed in a quiet, well-lit environment free from distracting stimuli. Before each assessment, participants received a detailed explanation of the procedure, and proper positioning was ensured throughout the evaluations. Short rest intervals were provided between assessments to prevent fatigue from influencing the measurement outcomes.

Cervical range of motion was evaluated using the Cervical Range of Motion (CROM) device. Participants were seated upright on a chair with back support, ensuring that their feet were in full contact with the ground. The device was positioned on the frontal region, and flexion, extension, and lateral flexion movements were measured using gravity-dependent goniometers, while rotation movements were assessed using a magnetic compass system. During the assessment, the trunk and thoracic region were stabilized to isolate cervical movements. Each motion was performed three times, and the mean value of the recorded angles was used for analysis. Participants were instructed to perform active movements within their pain-free range. The CROM device has been previously demonstrated to be an objective and reliable tool for measuring cervical range of motion (Rheault et al., 1992).

Postural assessment was performed using the New York Posture Rating Scale (NYPRS). Participants were observed in a natural standing position from the anterior, lateral, and posterior views. Thirteen anatomical segments—including the head, shoulders, thoracic region, pelvis, knees, and feet—were scored based on alignment accuracy. Each segment was rated on a scale from 1 to 5, where 5 represented ideal alignment and 1 indicated marked postural deviation. The total score reflected the participant's overall postural alignment. This method provides a systematic and reliable approach for evaluating posture in clinical settings (McRoberts et al., 2013).

Quality of life was assessed using the Short Form-36 (SF-36) questionnaire. The Turkish version of the scale, for which validity and reliability have been established, was administered through face-to-face interviews with participants. The SF-36 consists of 36 items evaluating eight subdomains: physical function, role physical, role emotional, vitality, mental health, social function, bodily pain, and general health. Each subscale is scored between 0 and 100, with higher scores indicating better quality of life. The SF-36 is a reliable instrument that comprehensively assesses both the physical and psychosocial components of health status (Demiral et al., 2006).

Statistical Analysis

All statistical analyses were performed using the Jamovi 2.6 software (The jamovi project, 2025). The distribution characteristics of the data were assessed through visual methods (histogram and Q-Q plots) and analytical tests, and the variables were determined to be non-normally distributed. Therefore, non-parametric tests were used for statistical comparisons. The Mann-Whitney U test was employed to compare continuous variables between the groups, while the Chi-square test was used for categorical variables. A p -value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

The sample size of the study was calculated using the G*Power 3.1.9.7 software. For an independent samples t -test, the parameters were set as $\alpha = 0.01$, power $(1-\beta) = 0.80$, and an effect size of approximately $d = 0.97$ derived from pilot data. The power analysis indicated that at least 27 participants were required per group. Accordingly, the study was completed with a total of 54 participants, including 27 individuals in the hypertension group and 27 in the control group.

RESULTS

No significant differences were found between the groups in terms of age, gender distribution, height, weight, systolic blood pressure, and diastolic blood pressure ($p > 0.05$) (Table 1). These findings indicate that the groups were demographically and clinically comparable at baseline.

When cervical range of motion was evaluated, the hypertension group demonstrated marked limitations across all planes. Flexion, extension, right and left rotation, and right and left lateral flexion movements were significantly lower in the hypertension group compared to the control group ($p < 0.05$) (Table 2).

Table 1. Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of the Participants

	CG (n=27)	HG (n=27)	p
Age (Years)	55.13±8.51	59.46±8.55	0.085
Gender (%)	Female	12 (22.22%)	0.774
	Male	15 (27.77%)	
Height (cm)	169.13±7.65	167.17±8.35	0.402
Weight (kg)	76.04±11.70	81.50±13.44	0.140
SBP (mmHg)	122.71±11.63	129.25±11.68	0.058
DBP (mmHg)	76.92±8.05	78.21±9.63	0.617

Values are presented as mean ± standard deviation or n (%). HT: Hypertension group; CG: Control group; SBP: Systolic blood pressure; DBP: Diastolic blood pressure. Mann-Whitney U test and Chi-square test were used. $p < 0.05$ was considered significant

Table 2. Intra-group Comparison of Cervical Range of Motion

Cervical ROM	CG (n=27)	HG (n=27)	p
Flexion	53.79±13.01	42.67±12.21	0.010*
Extension	67.38±17.88	51.63±15.81	0.001*
Right rotation	60.83±22.12	48.17±15.29	0.012*
Left rotation	59.67±19.78	49.33±11.41	0.021*
Right lateral flexion	41.17±9.74	34.83±9.57	0.048*
Left lateral flexion	45.25±9.90	37.25±7.24	0.006*

Values are presented as mean ± standard deviation (degrees). HT: Hypertension group; CG: Control group; ROM: Range of motion. Mann-Whitney U test used. $p < 0.05$ considered significant.

In the postural analysis, comparison of total scores from the NYPRS revealed significantly lower values in the hypertension group, indicating poorer overall postural alignment compared to the control group ($p < 0.01$) (Table 3).

Table 3. Intra-group Comparison of Posture Scores

	CG (n=27)	HG (n=27)	p
NYPRS Score	53.04±10.01	45.33±9.45	0.009*

Scores are presented as mean ± standard deviation. HT: Hypertension group; CG: Control group. NYPRS Score: Total score based on the New York Posture Rating Scale. Mann-Whitney U test used. $p < 0.05$ considered significant.

In the SF-36 quality-of-life assessment, no significant differences were observed between the groups in physical function, role physical, role emotional, vitality, social function, bodily pain, and general health ($p > 0.05$). However, the mental health subdomain scores were significantly lower in the hypertension group compared to the control group ($p < 0.01$) (Table 4).

Table 4. Intra-group Comparison of SF-36 Quality of Life Scores Between

SF-36	CG (n=27)	HG (n=27)	p
Physical function	87.75±18.15	78.44±24.61	0.084
Role physical	77.08±38.95	90.63±27.20	0.161
Role emotional	95.96±20.44	93.88±25.04	0.563
Vitality	67.50±21.47	56.38±18.50	0.091
Mental health	79.83±11.03	66.88±13.10	0.002*
Social function	85.88±23.39	93.06±15.55	0.095
Bodily pain	87.83±24.71	89.44±16.06	0.922
General health	65.42±17.25	63.75±14.20	0.708

Values are presented as mean ± standard deviation. HT: Hypertension group; CG: Control group; SF-36: Short Form-36 Health Survey. Mann-Whitney U test used. $p < 0.05$ considered significant.

DISCUSSION

This study was designed to examine cervical range of motion, postural alignment, and quality of life in individuals with hypertension. The findings demonstrated that participants with hypertension exhibited more restricted cervical mobility, poorer postural alignment, and lower quality of life, particularly in the mental health domain, compared to healthy controls. These results highlight that the assessment of

hypertension should not be limited to cardiovascular parameters alone, but should also take into account cervical function, posture, and psychosocial status.

In this study, cervical range of motion in individuals with hypertension was found to be significantly reduced compared to the control group. The literature indicates that cervical mobility is closely associated with posture, muscle tone, and proprioception. Forward head posture and increased biomechanical loading in the cervical segments have been reported to restrict neck movements, particularly in flexion, extension, and rotation (Fernández-de-las-Peñas et al., 2006; Sobrinho, et al., 2023; García-Pérez-Juana et al., 2018). However, to the best of our knowledge, no previous study has specifically investigated cervical mobility in individuals with hypertension. The results of our study suggest that hypertension may have adverse effects on cervical mobility, highlighting the clinical importance of evaluating cervical function in this population.

In this study, postural alignment was found to be more impaired in individuals with hypertension compared to healthy controls. Previous research has shown that forward head posture and increased thoracic kyphosis elevate biomechanical loading on the cervical region and negatively affect musculoskeletal function (Fernández-de-las-Peñas et al., 2006). Long-term postural alterations have also been demonstrated to restrict cervical mobility and proprioception, and potentially contribute to pain (García-Pérez-Juana et al., 2018). Additionally, individuals with forward head posture have been reported to exhibit significantly higher peripheral arterial pressure, suggesting a possible association between postural patterns and circulatory regulation (Kadu et al., 2019). Studies showing that postural correction interventions may improve blood pressure further support the idea that posture could serve as a potential interface between the cardiovascular and neuromuscular systems (Malik et al., 2023). Consistent with these findings, our results indicate impaired postural control in individuals with hypertension and highlight the importance of considering postural assessment as part of hypertension management.

In this study, health-related quality of life was found to be lower in individuals with hypertension, particularly in the domain of mental well-being. The negative impact of hypertension on quality of life has been documented in the literature across both physical and psychosocial dimensions. Individuals with hypertension have been reported to experience reduced emotional status, energy levels, and social participation, along with more frequent anxiety, stress, and fatigue (Carvalho et al., 2013). Moreover, a bidirectional relationship has been described between hypertension, mood changes, and the autonomic nervous system, with psychological stress potentially influencing disease progression (Bajkó et al., 2012). Social determinants and health inequities have also been shown to shape quality of life in hypertensive individuals, with socioeconomic burden and illness perception contributing to lower life satisfaction (Chaturvedi et al., 2024). Nevertheless, some studies have indicated that antihypertensive treatment may stabilize physical components of quality of life, and physical function decline may not be prominent in all patients (Trevisol et al., 2011). In line with these findings, while no significant differences were observed in physical functioning in our study, a marked reduction in mental well-being was identified, highlighting that the psychological and emotional effects of hypertension may be more pronounced.

This study highlights the clinical importance of assessing cervical mobility, posture, and quality of life in individuals with hypertension. The findings suggest that incorporating physical function and psychological well-being into hypertension management may support a more holistic care approach. Simple postural assessments and cervical mobility tests in primary care may help identify individuals at risk earlier. Future large-scale longitudinal and intervention studies are needed to clarify the effects of postural correction and exercise programs on blood pressure, functional capacity, and quality of life in this population.

Limitations

This study has several limitations. The cross-sectional design prevents interpretation of the observed associations in terms of causality. The sample was drawn from a single center and included a relatively small number of participants, which may limit the generalizability of the findings. In addition, postural assessment was performed using an observational method, and some measures relied on self-report, which may increase the potential for response and measurement bias.

CONCLUSION

This study comparatively evaluated cervical range of motion, posture, and quality of life in individuals with hypertension. The findings demonstrated that people with hypertension have markedly reduced cervical mobility, impaired postural alignment, and decreased quality of life, particularly in the mental health dimension.

These results indicate that hypertension should not be considered solely a cardiovascular condition, but should also be evaluated together with musculoskeletal function and psychosocial health. Routine screening of cervical function and posture in clinical practice may contribute to a more holistic approach in hypertension management. In addition, postural correction and functional exercise programs may have the potential to improve overall health status in individuals with hypertension. Future studies with larger populations, longitudinal designs, and intervention-based clinical trials are recommended to more clearly examine the causal dynamics of this relationship.

Conflict of Interest

There is no conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

Plan, design: EA, EUE, RY; **Material, methods and data collection:** BC, DAY, İÖ, EA, EUE, RY; **Data analysis and comments:** EA, EUE, RY; **Writing and corrections:** EA, EUE, RY.

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